

CHARACTERISTICS OF ADULT EDUCATION IN THE CONDITIONS OF DIGITALIZATION

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Abstract. *Digitization is a power for solving the main problems in education in the 21st century. Digitization has transformed learning and teaching spaces from traditional methods of classroom or lecture teaching to a virtual electronic platform. With digital technology, everyone has the opportunity to basic education, including elders. This article talks about digitization of education and features of adult education. Digitization in education has proven to be the right way to save resources, time and money. Today, the concept of continuous education is relevant and is aimed at realizing the potential of every person, regardless of age. Adults rarely have the opportunity to study every time. Therefore, working citizens are offered the opportunity of evening, part-time, distance education, as well as study abroad. A modern specialist should have the ability to learn continuously and acquire new knowledge, skills and abilities. Only this will allow you to keep up with the times and be considered a high-level specialist. Adult learning and education provides people with the opportunity to acquire the necessary knowledge, skills, virtues and values to develop and realize their rights and become the owners of their own destinies.*

Keywords: *digitization, adults, technique, technology, concept, computer, e-books, educational programs, internet, distance education, seminar, webinar.*

We live in an age of great ideas and technological advancements in education. Digitization of education means the use of digital technologies for teaching students. Computer-assisted test taking, online universities, e-books, and educational software are just a few examples of digitization of education today. Digitization has undoubtedly changed our education system, proving to be the right way to save resources in education. Today, digital technologies are actively used in all spheres of life. They serve the rapid development of the economy, banking, service sector, as well as the educational process. All citizens living in the country, including young children and pensioners, are forming the opinion that all problems in society can be solved through digital technologies [3].

Digital education is opening wide doors for students to acquire knowledge. Now you can access courses almost anywhere as long as you have an internet connection. It is not only full-time education, but also brings different, older groups of people into the same learning space, which may be missed in the localized education format.

What is adult education?

Despite the fact that the term "adult education" has found its place in the scientific-methodological literature of our country and abroad, in our opinion, this concept is among the concepts that encourage deep reflection.

By "**adult education**" we mean the all-round development of an adult. Any work related to expanding the knowledge, skills, and abilities of an adult is adult education. Another interesting case related to this term - who can be called an adult? - comes an inviting thought.

Most of the time, seniors mean people over 30 and even retirees. But any person who has a secondary education and starts to earn money independently is considered an adult [1].

Adults rarely have the opportunity to study full time. Therefore, working citizens are offered the opportunity of evening, part-time, distance education, as well as study abroad.

Adults are people who conduct educational activities in the social, industrial, family-household strata of society along with practical participation or alternately:

- develop their skills,
- enrich their knowledge, skills, personal qualities and spiritual values,
- acquire a new profession or improve their skills, or apply them in new directions to meet the needs of society and individuals.

In the last half century, adult education has been playing a leading role in the development of the field of education as a whole. Its development in terms of quantity and quality has become the main task of modern education all over the world.

Quantitatively, adult education covers 20-80% of the adult population in the developed countries of the world. In recent years, the number of people learning at an older age is increasing due to the fact that adult education creates ample opportunities for the education of representatives of the marginalized social group of society (socially vulnerable groups: pensioners, unemployed, women, disabled people, etc.).

At the quality level, the main concepts and types of education in the field of adult education are being formed, developed and implemented. These are continuous, free, distance, person-oriented education and others. Various forms and methods of organizing education are widely used in adult education. For example, continuing education, remedial education, blended learning courses, weekend study courses, etc.

New meaningful programs are being created and successfully implemented, such as civic and environmental education, which meet the various needs of older people.

Why do Catalans study?

- Satisfy curiosity, find an answer to a question.
- Enjoying using new skills in life.
- Enjoy reading.
- Meeting people with common interests.
- Certificate of education.
- Other reasons.

Adults are worried about their lack of confidence in their ability to study, and fear that in the process of studying, their illiteracy and inability to read will become known. Such stressors and experiences associated with learning in adults resist sustained and sustained motivation. As we know, in pedagogy it is necessary to study personal, physiological, psychological, social and professional characteristics in organizing the education of adults.

Each learner receives and acquires information strictly individually, depending on his psychophysiological characteristics and individual characteristics. Therefore, it is important to find out the functional literacy of the learner, which is determined by the success of the performance of the main vital functions by the adult before the beginning of the study [2].

According to the data of sociologists of Moscow State University, in the last 100 years, the volume of necessary knowledge has increased 100 times, and the speed of information

transmission has increased 10 million times. Life does not stand still, therefore, constant learning is an urgent need for a modern person.

It is for this reason that large budget funds are allocated to additional professional education in economically developed countries. In addition, its cost is compared with the budgetary funds allocated for higher education. This leads to clear results. For example, American experts concluded that additional education for adults provides 40% of economic growth in the country.

Digital technologies are essential for training, adult learning and human resource development in many organizations. The increasing use of technologically mediated environments enables flexible, ubiquitous and on-demand access to learning materials. For example, employees can develop their knowledge and skills in training management systems, webinars.

The main feature of adult education is the continuous growth of the learner's role in organizing his own learning process.

An adult learner has a sufficient level of self-awareness, life experience, and a sense of responsibility for active and practical participation in the organization, implementation, and evaluation of the educational process, he understands the purpose of education and the acquired knowledge. Understands the ways of practical application of skills, personal virtue, spiritual values. He also has the opportunity to carry out independent educational activities, which are of primary importance in the educational process.

The main feature of adult education is the leading role of the adult learner in his educational process, the main idea of the development of the entire field of education is to free the learner from the strict limits of the educational system, his determines and always determines the idea of increasing its role in the educational process.

Adult education is aimed at achieving the highest level of freedom, acquiring knowledge, skills, qualifications, and personal qualities. As a result, a person organizes his own educational process and becomes an independent learner.

It should be noted that adult education is primarily aimed at meeting the educational needs of a particular person. The diversity of the essence, form and methods of teaching in adult education, flexible, non-standard forms of educational organization allow to meet various individual educational needs of a certain person.

American scientist Malcolm Knowles identified five characteristics that affect adult learning:

Self-awareness. Adult students may already have an understanding of their goals and values. They have principles and beliefs and they know their priorities in life.

Gain experience. Adults probably have enough life experience at the time of learning that can help and hinder learning.

Willingness to learn. Adults decide for themselves whether they are ready to learn, why they need it, whether learning is appropriate for their goals or not.

Application direction. Adults learn to solve real-world problems, and learning becomes more attractive if they can immediately apply what they have learned.

Internal motivation to learn. The more mature a person is, the more intrinsic motivation he has. Adult learners learn because they recognize the need to learn, not because they are forced or told to.

The uniqueness of adult education requires a different approach from the teacher. The teacher should spend more time anticipating the students' level of experience and determining what the student wants to know about the subject. With digital learning, it's simple for the student and teacher to have a one-on-one private conversation if a student is struggling in a particular area or has the potential to learn more with a particular method. Learners can quickly and easily access tutors if they need extra help.

It is right that we devote time and effort to learning the best ways to use digital technology in adult education. However, we must not forget that adult learning is accomplished through personal relationships, and the best adult educators are able to create, maintain, and use them to support adults in their learning.

Digital education should enhance learning, not just continue it through digital tools. We need to explore ways to integrate technology so that students can actively engage with their ideas and peers, thereby enhancing the learning experience, increasing motivation, and providing learning experiences that are closer to or replicate the methods used by adults. should be done. access information and communicate with each other in the world outside the adult classroom [8].

Additional benefits of digitization for adult education

- Learners can learn at their own convenience
- The possibility of learning almost anywhere
- Choosing topics is easier than ever
- Learning can continue regardless of bad weather
- Time and money spent on going to class will be saved
- Digital learning is generally less expensive than classroom learning

To sum up, as we live in a borderless age where technology takes over all areas, adults, along with other participants in education, should be active participants in this process. At this stage, the educational system is developing with the aim of improvement, because their interest is very high and they cannot be satisfied by the previously developed educational systems. Because an adult student is a mature person with a leading role in the educational process, he sets clear educational goals and strives for independence, self-realization, and self-management. strives So we have to use digitization in our education system.

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